

Rapid Generation of the Scalar Spherical Multipole Translation Matrix Using a New Set of Recurrence Relations

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Introduction

The scalar spherical multipole translation coefficient (SSMTC) plays an important role in many areas of science and engineering involving wave phenomena[1]. Its importance stems from the facts that the scalar Green's function is translationally invariant and that it can be expanded in terms of scalar spherical multipoles. In electromagnetics, the dyadic Green's function can be expanded in terms of transverse vector spherical multipole fields, and their translation coefficients can be expressed in terms of SSMTCs[2][7]. In the acoustic and electromagnetic T-matrix multiple scattering equations, the SSMTC and vector spherical multipole translation coefficients (VSMTC) represent the strengths of the coupling between two spatially separated multipoles[1]. When one attempts to solve these equations on a computer, one computational bottleneck is to compute and store the multipole translation matrix. To reduce this computational burden, [3] discusses the respective symmetry relations of SSMTCs and VSMTCs. These symmetry relations are shown to reduce both the CPU and memory requirements of the scalar [4] and vector[5] T-matrix multiple scattering equation solution methods. Another way to reduce the computation time is to evaluate the SSMTC values using recurrence relations[6][7]. After reviewing the recurrence relations that form the basis of the present-day recursive SSMTC computation technique[6], we propose a procedure based on a new set of recurrence relations and compare its performance with that of [6].

The Scalar Spherical Multipole Translation Matrix

The spherical multipole field, $\phi_{l,m}(\bar{r})$, of order (l,m) is defined as $\phi_{l,m}(\bar{r}) \equiv h_l(kr)Y_{l,m}(\hat{r})$, where $h_l(kr)$ is the spherical Hankel function of order l with k representing the wavenumber, and $Y_{l,m}(\hat{r})$ is the spherical harmonics of order (l,m) with $Y_{l,-m}(\hat{r}) = (-1)^m Y_{l,m}^*(\hat{r})$. Under translation $\bar{r}' = \bar{r} + \bar{d}$ with $r > d$, $\phi_{l,m}(\bar{r}')$ can be written in terms of the regular part of $\phi_{l',m'}(\bar{d})$, $Rg\phi_{l',m'}(\bar{d}) = j_{l'}(kd) \cdot Y_{l',m'}(\hat{d})$ [2],

$$\phi_{l,m}(\bar{r}') = \sum_{l',m'} \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r}) \cdot Rg\phi_{l',m'}(\bar{d}) \quad (1)$$

Here, $\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$ is the SSMTC[1][2], and its brute-force evaluation is based on

$$\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r}) = \sum_{l''=|l-l'|,2}^{l+l'} \mathcal{L}_{l',m'}^{l,m}(l'') \cdot h_{l''}(kr)Y_{l'',m-m'}(\hat{r}), \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_{l',m'}^{l,m}(l'') = \Gamma_{l',m'}^{l,m}(l'')\mathcal{C}(l,l'',0,0,0)\mathcal{C}(l,l'',-m,m',-m+m')$ with $\Gamma_{l',m'}^{l,m}(l'') = i^{(l'-l+l'')(-1)^{m'}}[4\pi(2l+1)(2l'+1)/(2l''+1)]^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $\mathcal{C}(\dots; \dots)$ representing the

Clebsch-Gordan coefficient. In many applications, including the aforementioned multiple scattering calculations, $\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$ need to be evaluated for all combinations of (l, m) and (l', m') with $0 \leq l, l' \leq L_{max}$ for some L_{max} . Therefore, the evaluation of the translation matrix using (3) is computationally expensive and it is desirable to evaluate it using recurrence relations to reduce the high computational cost.

Recurrence Relations Resulting from $\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$

A set of recurrence relations[6][7] can be obtained by applying the differential operator, $\partial_i \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}$, to $\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$. It is convenient to work with the spherical basis vectors, r_μ , that are related to $\bar{r} = (x, y, z)$ through $r_\pm = \mp(x \pm iy)/\sqrt{2}$ and $r_0 = z$. Since $\phi_{l,m}(\bar{r})$ satisfies the Helmholtz equation, $\partial_\mu \phi_{l,m}(\bar{r})$ does as well. Furthermore, since $\phi_{l,m}(\bar{r})$ form a complete orthogonal basis set, $\partial_\mu \phi_{l,m}(\bar{r})$ may be written as a linear combination of $\phi_{l',m'}(\bar{r})$, and according to [8], $\frac{1}{k} \cdot \partial_\mu \phi_{l,m}(\bar{r})$ can be written as

$$\frac{1}{k} \cdot \partial_\mu \phi_{l,m}(\bar{r}) = a_{l,m,\mu} \cdot \phi_{l+1,m+\mu}(\bar{r}) + b_{l,m,\mu} \cdot \phi_{l-1,m+\mu}(\bar{r}) \phi_{l',m'}(\bar{r}) \quad (3)$$

with $a_{l,m,\mu} = (-1)^\mu \sqrt{\frac{l+1}{2l+1}} \mathcal{C}(l+1, 1, l; m+\mu, -\mu, m)$ and $b_{l,m,\mu} = (-1)^\mu \sqrt{\frac{l}{2l+1}} \mathcal{C}(l-1, 1, l; m+\mu, -\mu, m)$. Since ∂_μ is translationally invariant, its application to (1) results in the following three recurrence relations with $\mu = -1, 0, 1$:

$$a_{l,m,\mu} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l+1,m} + b_{l,m,\mu} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l-1,m+\mu} = c_{l',m',\mu} \cdot \alpha_{l'+1,m'-\mu}^{l,m} + d_{l',m',\mu} \cdot \alpha_{l'-1,m'-\mu}^{l,m} \quad (4)$$

where $c_{l',m',\mu} = (-1)^\mu \sqrt{\frac{l'+1}{2l'+3}} \mathcal{C}(l', 1, l'+1; m', -\mu, m'-\mu)$ and $d_{l',m',\mu} = (-1)^\mu \sqrt{\frac{l'}{2l'-1}} \mathcal{C}(l', 1, l'-1; m', -\mu, m'-\mu)$. (4) forms the basis of a procedure[6] that recursively generates $\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$ for all combinations of (l, m) and (l', m') from the seed values of $\alpha_{l'',m''}^{0,0}(\bar{r})$. Even though this procedure is efficient and straightforward to implement, one drawback is that, if one wants to generate $\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$ with $l, l' \leq L_{max}$, it is necessary to pre-compute and store the $\alpha_{l'',m''}^{0,0}(\bar{r})$ values with $0 \leq l'' \leq 2L_{max}$ and to perform the recurrence calculations for $l' > L_{max}$. This is because the computation of $\alpha_{l',m'}^{l+1,m+\mu}(\bar{r})$ using (4) requires $\alpha_{l'+1,m'-\mu}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$. In this paper, we propose a procedure, based on a new set of recurrence relations, that requires the seed values of $\alpha_{l'',m''}^{0,0}(\bar{r})$ with $l'' \leq L_{max} + 1$ and that is free of the need to perform the extraneous recurrence calculations for $l' > L_{max}$.

A New Set of Recurrence Relations

Taking a cue from the relation, $L_\mu(\bar{r})Y_{l,m}(\hat{r}) \equiv \frac{1}{i}(\bar{r} \times \nabla)_\mu Y_{l,m}(\hat{r}) = f_{l,m,\mu} Y_{l,m+\mu}(\hat{r})$ with $f_{l,m,\mu} \equiv (-1)^\mu \sqrt{l(l+1)} \mathcal{C}(l, 1, l; m+\mu, -\mu, m)$ [8] and using the fact that $L_\mu(\bar{r})$ acts only on the angular part, we infer $L_\mu(\bar{r}) \cdot \phi_{l,m}(\bar{r}) = f_{l,m,\mu} \cdot \phi_{l,m+\mu}(\bar{r})$. Application of $L_\mu(\bar{r}')$ to (1) with $L_\mu(\bar{r}') = L_\mu(\bar{r}) + L_\mu(\bar{d})$ then results in

$$L_\mu(\bar{r}) \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r}) = f_{l,m,\mu} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m+\mu}(\bar{r}) - f_{l',m'-\mu,\mu} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'-\mu}^{l,m}(\bar{r}) \quad (5)$$

Using $L_{\pm}(\bar{r}) = \pm(r_0 \cdot \partial_{\pm} - r_{\pm} \cdot \partial_0)$ and $L_0(\bar{r}) = r_- \cdot \partial_+ - r_+ \cdot \partial_-$ and (3) for $\partial_{\mu} \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$,

$$L_- \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m} = f_{l,m,-1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m-1} - f_{l',m'+1,-1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'+1}^{l,m} \quad (6)$$

$$= kr_- (a_{l,m,0} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l+1,m} + b_{l,m,0} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l-1,m}) - kr_0 (a_{l,m,-1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l+1,m-1} + b_{l,m,-1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l-1,m-1})$$

$$L_0 \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m} = (f_{l,m,0} - f_{l',m',0}) \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m} \quad (7)$$

$$= kr_- (a_{l,m,1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l+1,m+1} + b_{l,m,1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l-1,m+1}) - kr_+ (a_{l,m,-1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l+1,m-1} + b_{l,m,-1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l-1,m-1})$$

$$L_+ \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m} = f_{l,m,1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m+1} - f_{l',m'-1,1} \alpha_{l',m'-1}^{l,m} \quad (8)$$

$$= kr_0 (a_{l,m,1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l+1,m+1} + b_{l,m,1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l-1,m+1}) - kr_+ (a_{l,m,0} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l+1,m} + b_{l,m,0} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l-1,m}).$$

Several different procedures can be formulated from (6)-(8). However, care must be exercised to ensure that they remain stable as $|r_0| \rightarrow 0$ or $|r_{\pm}| \rightarrow 0$. A procedure is sketched here that is based on the application of the null operator, $\nabla \cdot \bar{L}(\bar{r})$ to $\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$. Using $\sum_{\mu=-1}^1 (-1)^{\mu} f_{l,m,\mu} \cdot \{a, b, c, d\}_{l,m+\mu,-\mu} = 0$, $\nabla \cdot \bar{L}(\bar{r}) \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$ leads to

$$f_{l',m'-1,1} \left[a_{l,m,-1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'-1}^{l+1,m-1} + b_{l,m,-1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'-1}^{l-1,m-1} \right] \quad (9)$$

$$= f_{l',m',0} \left[a_{l,m,0} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l+1,m} + b_{l,m,0} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l-1,m} \right] - f_{l',m'+1,-1} \left[a_{l,m,1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'+1}^{l+1,m+1} + b_{l,m,1} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'+1}^{l-1,m+1} \right]$$

Let $\tilde{\alpha}^{l,m}(\bar{r}) \equiv \{\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r}); 0 \leq l' \leq L_{max}, |m'| \leq l'\}$. (9) can be used to compute $\tilde{\alpha}^{l+1,m-1}(\bar{r})$ for $1 \leq m \leq l$ once $\tilde{\alpha}^{l+1,l+1}(\bar{r})$, $\tilde{\alpha}^{l+1,l}(\bar{r})$ and $\tilde{\alpha}^{l-1,m \pm \mu}(\bar{r})$ are known. The $\tilde{\alpha}^{l+1,l+1}(\bar{r})$ and $\tilde{\alpha}^{l+1,l}(\bar{r})$ values can be computed from $\tilde{\alpha}^{p,q}(\bar{r})$ with $p < l+1$ using the recurrence relations that result from $L_+(\bar{r}) \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,l}(\bar{r})$, $L_+(\bar{r}) \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,l-1}(\bar{r})$ and $L_0(\bar{r}) \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,l}(\bar{r})$. The $\tilde{\alpha}^{l+1,-m}(\bar{r})$ values with $0 < m \leq l+1$ can then be obtained from $\tilde{\alpha}^{l+1,m}(\bar{r})$ using the symmetry relation, $\alpha_{p',q'}^{p,q}(\bar{r}) = (-1)^{q-q'} e^{i2(q-q')\phi} \alpha_{p',-q'}^{p,-q}(\bar{r})$ [4], where ϕ is the spherical azimuth angle of \bar{r} .

Discussion

Fig. 1 compares, as a function of L_{max} , the CPU time of the new recursive method with those of the brute-force method based on (2) and the recursive method of [6] for 64 \bar{r} points. For a given L_{max} , there are $(L_{max} + 1)^4$ combinations of (l, m) and (l', m') for $\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$ with $0 \leq l, l' \leq L_{max}$. Thus, the two recursive methods scale as $\mathcal{O}(L_{max}^4)$, while the brute-force method scales as $\mathcal{O}(L_{max}^5)$ because of the summation over l'' in (2). Comparison of (9) with (4) shows that (9) requires more floating point operations than (4). However, Fig. 1.b confirms that the new recursive procedure based on (9) is more efficient than the one based on (4) because it does not require the extraneous recurrence calculations for $l' > L_{max}$.

Summary

We present a new set of recurrence relations of $\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$ that results from $L_{\mu}(\bar{r}) \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r}) = \frac{1}{i} (\bar{r} \times \nabla)_{\mu} \cdot \alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$. We then discuss a procedure that recursively

computes $\alpha_{l',m'}^{l,m}(\bar{r})$ for $0 \leq l, l' \leq L_{max}$ from the seed values of $\alpha_{l'',m''}^{0,0}(\bar{r})$ with $0 \leq l'' \leq L_{max} + 1$. We demonstrate its efficiency by comparing its CPU times with those of the brute-force method based on (2) and the recursive method [6] based on (4).

Figure 1: Timing comparisons, as a function of L_{max} , for 64 \bar{r} points.

References

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